

CloudNetIX Project
Technical Report
Monitoring and Visibility in 5G networks:
Opportunities and Criticalities
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Abstract

This document reports various 5G aspects that may challenge network monitoring. After an introductory section and an overview of the 3G-PPP roadmap, various challenges that spun up from adopting 5G and trends are presented. Each topic is treated separately in a dedicated section, and aspects relevant for monitoring are highlighted and discussed.

Introduction

5G requirements

5G opens the path to a **multipurpose mobile network**, accommodating multiple requirements for different service types. Three main service types – or **Use Cases** – has been identified by 3GPP:

- **eMBB** – or *enhanced Mobile Broadband* –provides greater bandwidth and large capacity requirements, complemented by moderate latency improvements on both 5G NR and 4G LTE. The initial phase of 5G NSA (Non-Standalone) deployments focuses on eMBB. Examples of eMBB services include AR/VR, 4K/8K audio and video, multi-party video chats, HD video applications etc.
- **mMTC** – or *massive Machine Type Communications* –aims to provide connectivity to a massive number of devices that require transmitting or receiving small data blocks, be sent on low bandwidth pipes, and provide services to latency-tolerant applications. mMTC was initially addressed as part of 3GPP Release 13/14 low power wide area (LPWA) technologies, including NB-IoT. Examples include medical care, the Internet of Vehicles, smart recognition etc.
- **URLLC** – or *Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications* –provides ultra-high reliability and ultralow latency support. It enables mission-critical applications such as allowing drones and driverless cars to be road safe. To be deployed, URLLC requires the 5G Core deployment for full end-2-end latency reduction, and it is expected to be developed in later deployments. Examples include smart manufacturing, autonomous vehicles, drones, remote surgery, VR live broadcast, etc.

To fulfil the **requirements** of these use cases, 5G targets at:

- Faster Speeds: up to 100 times higher than 4G.
- Lower Latency: lower network latencies (1 millisecond) than 4G (200 milliseconds).
- Higher Density: ten times as many connections in the same area as 4G.
- Lower Energy Consumption: 5G requires less energy than 4G, useful for resource-constrained devices.

5G enabling technologies

5G introduces several **enabling technologies** to achieve its performance goals and provide a truly multipurpose network. In [38], Akyildiz et al. anticipated the following major technological breakthroughs that would drive the next generation mobile networks: (1) wireless software-defined network (**SDN**), (2) network function virtualization (NFV), (3) **millimeter wave** spectrum, (4) **massive MIMO**, (5) **network ultra-densification**, (6) **big data and mobile cloud computing**, (7) **scalable Internet of Things**, (8) **device-to-device connectivity with high mobility**, (9) **green communications**, and (10) **new radio** access techniques

One of the main novelties in 5G that impact its architecture is the **replacement of traditional legacy equipment with cloudified elements**. The functionalities provided by the physical equipment are now logically transposed to the virtual environment. This substantial shift towards cloud computing and virtualization have repercussions from many angles.

In 5G, 3GPP defines two main components: a new 5G core network, the 5GC, replacing the EPC and a new radio access technology – the 5G New Radio (NR). The **Control and User plane separation** adopted by the latest 4G releases is also reflected in the new 5G core (5GC) and NR RAN.

The 5GC is based on a **Service Base Architecture (SBA)** framework. The 5G network control plane functionality and its common data repositories deployment are based on the concept of services. Instead of having dedicated monolithic services, available functionalities are organized in virtual network *Functions* or services (VNFs). These may be deployed in a monolithic way or distributed in many locations in the infrastructure. Being deployed as VNFs in a cloud environment, these services can be scaled up and down and migrated, depending on the need. SBA deploys a cloud-native 5G Core Network, decomposing software into smaller, more manageable pieces.

The 5G network paradigm, with the deployment of a cloud-native 5G Core, allows the Core network functions to be delivered from the cloud. This feature has captured the attention of the **Hyperscalers**, such as Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure and Google, which have developed their own roadmap for integrating with the telco world, entering into competition with infrastructure providers and, potentially, telcos themselves. Collaboration between telcos and Hyperscalers are already popping out ¹.

Another novelty introduced in the 5G infrastructure is the support of computational and storage resources near the radio access network inside the operator's network. The so called **Edge cloud** has been introduced to support the network in providing advanced services such as lower latency. Complementary to the 3GPP standardization activity, ETSI has initiated the ETSI MEC ISG to provide a standard based framework for Multiple access Edge Computing and a 3GPP synergized architecture.

Virtualization is also introduced in the Radio Access Network (RAN), with the definition of the **disaggregated RAN** that allows the RAN to be split and different components virtualized.

Another important introduction of 5G is native network slicing. **Network Slicing** allows accommodating services with different and divergent requirements (e.g. eMBB, URLLC and mMTC) in the same mobile network. This is possible thanks to the technological enablers

¹ <https://techmonitor.ai/5g/what-is-cloud-native-5g>

introduced by 5G, such as cloud computing and virtualization, that allow deploying slicing natively.

As the complexity of the network increases and new capabilities are required, the introduction of advanced automation tools and mechanisms is required to improve the resources' performance, reliability, and efficiency. In this context, artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) tools and support start gaining attention, both in application deployment support and in network automation. Indeed, 5G deployments are complex and need automation tools to reach maximum performance and optimal resource allocation, zero-touch management, and security services. Consequently, getting operational data timely and efficiently for feeding AI/ML algorithms (to provide prediction and optimizations) is a must: indeed, collecting data (and pre-processing) for training an ML model is a basic step in machine learning pipeline. Predictions can only be as good as the data on which they have been trained.

3GPP has introduced network Data Analytics Functions (NWDAFs) in 5G to perform centralized data collection/analytics to address this aspect. NWDAFs provides network analysis information upon request from other network functions of the 5G Core (e.g. the load level information of a particular network slice). They are an evolution of the RAN Congestion Awareness Function (RCAF) from previous 3GPP releases, and it is still in an early stage of standardization.

Visibility into end-to-end subscriber sessions may span **multiple network domains**, including physical and virtualized (virtual machine [VM]- and container-based) and multiple vendors. **Multiple borders should be considered**, e.g., borders between domains (core, radio access network [RAN], transport, access, data centre, etc.) and between technologies (3G, 4G, 5G, cloud, etc.). Typically, each technological domain has its own peculiarities from the monitoring point of view. With the 5G move to network functions virtualization (NFV – itself a prerequisite for 5G), monitoring may be required at the physical infrastructure (switches, routers, etc.) and at the servers that support virtualized network functions.

Challenges for monitoring

The **increase in the volume and complexity of traffic expected to be carried** by 5G networks is becoming a challenge for monitoring. Also, 5G architecture comprises **multiple technology architectures**: operators legacy telco infrastructure, new software-defined networks, and cloud computing. Besides, multiple radio access technologies may run in parallel. While some early adopters may be clamouring for 5G, other types of services might depend on 2G connectivity, such as some IoT services.

The ability of 5G networks **to support demanding applications (eMBB, mMTC, URLLC)** and deliver guaranteed latency for mission-critical applications will also depend on how it will be able to introduce automation into the loop. To this aim, new tools for network visibility and monitoring are needed.

For dealing with complexity, the **level of automation** of operations should be increased not only to reduce the cost but also to assure an appropriate level of reliability. At the same time, varied **and severe security threats** are introduced due to the extended attack surface. In many cases, the operator must act as the first line of defence for both enterprise and consumer customers.

New, on-demand services requiring strict QoS requirements require advanced and new techniques in **virtualization and softwarization**. These are being introduced both at the radio and core network, enabling high performance, low latency, and flexibility.

A crucial part of 5G is **the level of automation** that needs to be achieved for being able to take advantage of the 5G new features. Enabling these levels of automation requires introducing dynamicity to the radio and core network in contrast with the static architectures of the past, which makes it difficult to trace the root cause of the issues. Therefore, performance monitoring and analysis will be key to mobile network automation

Automation will depend on artificial intelligence (AI) and predictive analytics for being able to deal with the high amount of heterogeneous data. Indeed, 5G **brings enriched functionality** but more **network complexity**: the **amount of generated data** can easily go beyond the capacity of manual design, planning, and management.

New tools to **automatically analyze performance data, configuration parameters, and alarm data** started to be introduced and standardized. They are designed to be able to process a high amount of data to detect and fix network anomalies, give a much deeper insight into the inherent problems that may cause network service issues, and allow adopting proactive measures to prevent them from affecting QoS.

3GPP standard evolution

The Rel-16 Stage 3 has been recently completed, opening up to the first 5G deployments, and in particular to Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) use cases. Rel-17 Stage 2 is ongoing, focusing on ultrareliable low-latency communications (URLLC) and massive machine-type communications (mMTC). Current Ongoing Releases timelines are:

Figure 1 3GPP Evolution Roadmap

The adoption of the standard is foreseen in phases and heterogeneous environments are the result of this approach. In **Non Stand Alone (NSA)** deployments, both 4G and 5G co-exist, supported by dual connectivity and a 3G Core. As 5G deployment goes on, more **Stand Alone** deployments are expected (i.e. pure 5G). Nevertheless, heterogeneous environments will still be seen, such as mobile and WiFi dual connectivity (and Multiconnectivity).

CUPS – Control User Plane Separation

Control and User Plane Separation, or CUPS, refers to the separation of functionalities in the network core, and in particular between user plane functions and control plane functions. It was introduced to bring more flexibility to the network deployment and operations and allows for both centralized and distributed deployments.

Control and user plane separation (CUPS) architecture was first introduced in 4G with *3GPP Release 14*² at the packet data gateway level. In 4G, CUPS provides the architecture enhancements for the separation of functionality in the Evolved Packet Core's SGW, PGW and TDF. In CUPS, for example, the S/PGWs are de-composed to S/PGW-C (control plane), and S/PGW-U (user plane).

² <https://www.3gpp.org/news-events/1882-cups>

CUPS decomposition also drives the design of 5G architecture, for which CUPS is native and has been introduced in *3GPP's Release 15*³. In particular, the User Plane Function (UPF) plays a fundamental role in the packet processing of user traffic. Signalling processing is instead done by the NFs in the control plane, such as Session Management Function (SMF). CUPS allows placing control plane functions centralized while distributing UPF functions from central to the Edge.

In 5G, CUPS allows distributing Network Functions across the network. User and data plane functions can scale independently, enabling a more flexible deployment and dimensioning of the network. UPFs, which deal with data traffic forwarding, can be decentralized and scaled independently (e.g. when data traffic increases) without affecting the functionality of the existing nodes. The network can scale by deploying more UPFs that can be added without affecting the control plane functions. Control plane functions take care of the user connection management, the definition of QoS policies, user authentication, etc. . The disaggregation of control and user plane is fundamental for implementing some of the 5G capabilities, such as Edge computing and slicing.

CUPS also allows implementing *the user plane programmability*. Selected UPFs can be configured to assume a particular role (e.g., a data plane gateway, a regular transit router or switch) to perform forwarding, encapsulation, traffic steering or whatever else is needed according to the indications received by the control plane elements. Potentially, this enables the implementation of different data planes solutions to coexist in the same user plane. UPFs could be dynamically selected according to specific traffic needs. Data planes nodes encapsulate traffic when GPRS Tunneling Protocol for User Plane (GTP-U) is used for packet transportation, enforce steering policies to IP packets if a plain IP transport network approach is used, etc.

³ <http://www.3gpp.org/release-15>

Release 15 (3GPP TS 23.501)

Figure 2 5G architecture with CUPS highlighted (in green the analogous 4G functions)

CUPS and Network Disaggregated RAN

The decomposition of traditional BBU in Central Unit (CU) and Distributed Unit (DU) ease the transformation of their functionalities into virtualized or containerised network functions. This approach brings elasticity, scalability, and cost-efficiency. The CU-DU decomposition leverage the use of enhanced Common Public Radio Interface (eCPRI) and Open RAN (O-RAN).

The CUPS architecture is also adopted in the 5G NG RAN (Next Generation Radio Access Network) through RAN disaggregation. The CU can be split further into the central plane and user plane (defined in 3GPP TS 38.401):

- CU-CP (Central Unit Control Plane)
- CU-UP (Central Unit User Plane).

Figure 3 5G architecture with CUPS highlighted (CUPS extended to RAN) with Edge and Central Cloud

The use of 5G NG-RAN Fronthaul (CPRI/eCPRI), Midhaul (F1-C, F1-U interfaces), and Backhaul (NG interfaces) allow the CSP to distribute CU and DU functions to Telco Edge data centre. Being softwarezied, 5G RAN Functional Units can be deployed in several modalities, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 4 Location Flexibility for 5G RAN Functional Units (NGMN, 2018)

We can summarize the features of 5G in relation with CUPS as follows:

- Reconfiguration of LTE network function to support separation between data and user plane
- 5G native support for CUPS
- Architecture based on Virtualized NFs on commodity hardware
- Distributed UPFs to edge to reduce latency and backhaul traffic
- Enablement of standard-based MEC by supporting routing to local UPFs located at edge sites
- Extension of CUPS to include RAN: Central Unit (CU) split in user plane CU (CU-UP) and control plane CU (CU-CP)
- Enabling E2E network slicing by supporting independent paths for each service.

Aspects of CUPS relevant for monitoring

With CUPS, control and user flows are disaggregated: this may affect the monitoring strategies. The capability of correlating user and control plane flows on a per-subscriber, user device, RAN, or network slice basis increases the visibility across mobile network segments. Correlated user and data plane traffic can be sent to the monitoring and analysis tools, combined with other functionalities such as traffic intelligence, and gain deep insights into networks. Subscriber's control and data sessions are identified and passed to the analytics/monitoring probes able to provide an accurate view of the subscriber sessions. Subscriber-specific attributes relevant for monitoring and correlation include:

- the **subscriber ID**, allocated for each SIM, known as international mobile subscriber identity (**IMSI**) in 4G (and in NSA) and as subscriber permanent identifier (**SUPI**) in 5G;
- the **device ID**, known as the international mobile equipment identity (**IMEI**) in 4G and permanent equipment identifier (**PEI**) in 5G;
- the mobile station intelligent subscriber digital network (**MSISDN**) number;
- the E-UTRAN (4G) cell global identifier (**ECGI**) or NR (5G) cell global identifier (**NCGI**);
- the 5G network slice selection assistance information (**NSSAI**);
- various **mobile core logical interfaces** (e.g., Gn/Gp, S11/S1U, S5/S8, N11/N4, N4/N3) carried in HTTP/2 or GTP-C messages.

With CUPS, all data traffic generated by the UE (the user plane traffic) is carried within GTP-U tunnels established between the gNB and the UPFs, through the N3 interface. Each GTP-U tunnel is identified by tunnel endpoint ID (TEID). GTP-U TEIDs must be known and correlated to the subscriber-level attributes to enable the subscriber traffic to be processed in a subscriber-aware manner. Subscriber-aware monitoring policies that rely on correlation allow forwarding only relevant data to monitoring tools and increasing visibility on per-subscriber traffic useful for improving QoE, performance and security.

By considering user and control flows correlation, it is possible to send **all IP fragments** within a UE session to the same tool responsible for processing, leveraging various approaches: e.g. sampling, IMSI/SUPI, IMEI/PEI, ECGI/NCGI or NSSAI whitelisting.

Non Stand Alone (NSA) and Stand Alone (SA) Architectures

To allow a smooth transition from 4G to 5G, 3GPP has specified two main deployment options: the non-standalone (NSA) and the standalone (SA) deployments. While SA corresponds to a full 5G deployment, NSA configurations allow the integration of elements from 4G and 5G generations. The NSA architecture combines 5G NR radio cells with 4G LTE radio cells and 4G core (EPC). NSA depends entirely on the existing LTE network for all control functions and add-on services. The LTE infrastructure is responsible for service continuity and continuous coverage and, before that, core network. For the radio part, instead, it requires heavy integration between 4G and 5G radio using dual connectivity to provide radio access. 5G NR can be selectively deployed in areas with an expectedly high demand for data services.

Various network architecture options for NSA and SA architecture have been proposed to 3GPP and potential migration paths [39]. They are named after a number, from 1 to 8, even if not all are defined by 3GPP.

The most relevant SA options are 1, 2, and 5, where 1 is the 4G (LTE radio and EPC), 2 is the full 5G (NR and 5GCore), and 5 indicates a mixed option (LTE radio and 5GCore)

In NSA mode, LTE bands can be re-farmed to be used by NR in various combinations. More relevant NSA options are 3, 4 and 7. They can be further divided into different suboptions that identify different types of networking architecture corresponding to different user plane aggregation points and distribution flow types. In particular, they include the following suboptions:

- 3/7/4 support a split bearer
- 3a/7a/4a support a secondary cell group (SCG) bearer
- 3x/7x support an SCG split bearer

Initial deployments are based on LTE – NR Dual Connectivity. 3GPP Non-standalone (NSA) adopts Option 3 with 4G EPC (Evolved Packet Core), which allows deploying 5G NR gNodeB stations with a 4G EPC and mixed gNodeB/eNodeB stations. Option 3 is the deployment choice for the initial 5G services deployment.

The early deployments of the 5G NSA architecture focus on eMBB scenarios (mirroring the standardization path) and reuse the current EPC and LTE as the anchors. Anchors of the control plane are always located in the LTE RAN and the S1-C interface is terminated by eNB. This approach enables a quick introduction of 5G NR.

SA option 2 and NSA Option 3, particularly the NSA Option 3x, are the typical architectures supported by mobile network vendors and operators. Option 3 allows service providers to leverage their existing EPC deployments, and NR and LTE radios are deployed and supported by the existing EPC.

Options 5 & 7 (incl. 7x) may be considered as no longer prioritized. Options 6 and 8 were introduced in RP-161266 and shows a direct connection of NR to EPC without LTE dependence. However, there are no 3GPP plans to standardize them, although there have been some requests from India for Option 6.

Options 1/2/5 SA

Figure 5 Options 1/2/5 SA

Option 1 – SA LTE connected to EPC.

Option 2 – SA NR connected to 5GC. A full 5G Core is deployed, with its Service Base Architecture. The 5G NR radio cells handle both the control plane and user plane.

Option 5 – SA LTE connected to 5GC. Option 5 enables the use of new 5G core services in areas not yet served by NR. It also allows NR SA to LTE handover without interworking between EPC and 5G core when leaving the NR service.

Options 3/3a/3x NSA LTE and NR connected to EPC

Figure 6 Options 3/3a/3x NSA LTE and NR connected to EPC

Option 3 – Traffic is split across 4G and 5G at eNodeB. There is no direct connection between the NR and the 4G network. All 5G user and control plane traffic is routed through the 4G RAN.

Option 3a – Traffic is split across 4G and 5G at EPC (S-GW). It envisions the dynamic switching of the 5G user plane between the LTE RAN and NR. All of the control plane traffic is routed through the 4G RAN.

Option 3x – Traffic is split across 4G and 5G at 5G cell. It is a combination of Option 3 and 3a. Both the S1-U and X2 interfaces are available to the NR RAN. Data traffic from the NR RAN can be routed through the LTE RAN or directly to the LTE Core. All control plane traffic is routed through the 4G RAN.

All three options are transparent to MME and P-GW and translate to an E-RAB modification procedure at MME. Frequency, power, and antennae orientation must be configured for both 4G and 5G to ensure that overall coverage and performance is optimized. The control and user plane can be separated between LTE and NR to minimize the number of handovers between cells. In practice, when adding small 5G cells within a larger 4G macro cell, the 4G cell handles the control plane traffic. The UE (User Equipment) will always try to connect first to the radio delivers the best user plane connection: i.e. 5G when inside the small cell or 4G when outside the small cell's range. Operators need visibility into subscriber session performance to support early NSA scenarios across both 4G and 5G networks.

Options 4/4a NSA NR and LTE connected to 5GC

Figure 7 Options 4/4a NSA NR and LTE connected to 5GC

Option 4 – There is no Xn interface between the LTE RAN and NR. All the information flows via the Xn interface.

Option 4a – There is no Xn interface between the LTE RAN and NR. The LTE RAN is connected to the 5GC via the NG-U interface.

Option 4 is a critical configuration in the transition, even if not currently planned by all network or terminal suppliers, that allows NR SA UEs to access LTE carriers in addition to NR carriers. This option allows 5G core connected UEs to augment NR carriers with LTE carriers. This approach ensures that data rates remain competitive with those provided by NSA Option 3x.

Option 4 support interworking when moving between NR/5GC and LTE/EPC. Option 5 is then not required if all LTE sites are connected to the new core network (CN). There are three different scenarios where such interworking might be required. Moving between an NR/LTE site and an LTE-only site, moving deep indoors from mid-band NR to low band LTE when NR is not yet deployed in low bands and for on-demand NSA selection (alternative 2 to option 4).

Options 7/7a/7x NSA LTE and NR connected to 5GC

Figure 8 Options 7/7a/7x NSA LTE and NR connected to 5GC

Option 7 – There is no interface between the NR and the 5GC. Information flows via the Xn.

Option 7a – There is no Xn interface, and the NR is connected to the 5GC via the NG-U interface.

Option 7x – Is a combination of Option 7 and 7a

Options 7/7x enable dual connectivity with NR carriers added to the LTE master. These options make use of high-bandwidth NR expansion carriers with 5G core without the need to deploy a low-frequency NR anchor layer. Option 5 impacts the adaptation of Option 3x dual connectivity procedures to reflect new interfaces to the 5G core.

Migration path from SA Option 1 to NSA Option 3x

Migrating from Option 1 (4G EPC plus LTE) to Option 3x is straightforward. Option 3x is based on LTE assisted signalling, which is done through the LTE radio to the User Equipment (UE). The 5G radio will only establish a user plane connection to the EPC core via signalling from the LTE radio.

The early deployments of the 5G NSA architecture focus on eMBB scenarios (mirroring the standardization path) and reuse the current EPC and LTE as the anchors. This approach enables a quick introduction of 5G NR. The control plane's anchor is always located in the LTE RAN (S1-C interface is terminated by eNB).

Migration path from NSA Option 3x to SA Option 2

The path for migrating from Option 3x to Option 2 (i.e. 5G SA, with 5G NGC and 5G NR) comprises different options that could potentially be the next step after Option 3x. Differences in these options revolve around the extent of changes and the number of moving parts.

Aspects of NSA relevant for monitoring

Migration options in NSA include mixed architectures with 4G EPC, mixed NR and 4G radios, SBI and non SBI interfaces. In most cases, 5GC will be introduced in a second phase into the existing network, together with the increase of the 5G NR coverage area. As such, 5G networks get less dependent on the LTE infrastructure, even if this last will be maintained for service continuity. The EPC and 5GC may coexist for a long time. Since 5GC is not able to service subscribers with 4G-only UE, or early UE that supports only NSA, operators will not replace their EPC with 5GC unless 100% among their subscribers have 5G UE.

The master-slave structure 5G NSA architecture (where the 4G access node is the master and 5G access node is the slave) has several limitations. The 5G NR acts as a secondary access node controlled by an upgraded eNB as a master access node. This setup allows operators to offer eMBB services to end-users. Yet it introduces some complexities into network operations and service optimization, as it requires close interoperation between 4G and 5G networks. In addition, operators may need to upgrade the EPC capacity.

With 5G SA, operators will be able to offer all 5GC-dependent use cases and perform the E2E network slicing necessary to serve new verticals. However, the SA network will still interoperate with the existing 4G/LTE network to provide service continuity between the two network generations. Interoperation with the LTE network takes place to cover areas not yet covered by 5G and connect 5G users with non-5G users. Interoperation is confined to session handover and service continuity.

5G Core - Service Based Architecture (SBA)

This paragraph describes the key elements of the Service Based Architecture (SBA) and its functions. The complete cloud-native 5G core network architecture, standardized by 3GPP, is defined as 5G Service-Based Architecture (5G SBA). It is a service-based architecture based on Network Virtualization and the softwarization of NFs. Reflecting the CUPS architecture, data plane and control plane Network Functions (NFs) are separated and managed independently (e.g., for scaling and resource allocation). 5GC NFs may be therefore realized as software instances deployed on a virtual infrastructure instead of using physical network functions. NF services are exposed by the control plane. Interactions among NFs services are defined by Service-Based Interfaces (SBIs) [1].

User plane and Control plane Network Functions

Data plane NFs

The 5GC data plane comprises a set of NFs [2]: the User Equipment (UE), the Radio Access Network (RAN), the User Plane Function (UPF), and the Data Network (DN).

Control plane NFs

The 5G control plane includes the following NFs [2]: the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), the Authentication Server Function (AUSF), the Session Management Function (SMF), the Policy Control Function (PCF), the Network Slice Selection Function (NSSF), Unified Data Management (UDM), the Unified Data Repository (UDR), the Network Repository Function (NRF), the Network Exposure Function (NEF), and the Application Function (AF).

Figure 9 Service-Based Architecture (SBA) for the 5G network

SBA characteristics

The SBA is also a **stateless** architecture. However, NFs have the necessity to maintain context information of subscriber information or transport layer association information. In modern microservice-based software architectures, this can be achieved by using an external data store, thus decoupling the application layer and the data storage layer. This approach allows the persistence of data, even if the function encounters a sudden failure, thus allowing better reliability and resiliency. In 5SBA, the central database where NFs store their state information is called Unstructured Data Storage Function (UDSF). Making the NFs stateless means that they can be scaled easily and that specific NFs can be isolated in case of malfunctioning, thus allowing better optimization of resources and enabling service continuity.

The 5GC NFs can be implemented with a **micro-services** architecture. This allows to implement both micro-services that are *NF-specific* (specific to, e.g., AMF like N1/N2 communication, mobile termination, N1/N2 interface) as well as micro-services that are used by all NF (e.g., interface, DB, event). Micro-services specific for Operations, Administration, Maintenance are also implemented (e.g., logging and tracing). Each NF's micro-service runs in a separate container, independently scalable and re-usable. Since containers have low overheads, micro-services can be quickly and easily installed, enabling rapid service deployment.

The Service Based interface (SBI)

With the SBA, 3GPP also introduces the Service Based Interface (SBI) between control plane functions. The 5G SBI adopts a web-based communications model, replacing the point-to-point reference point-based interface typical of the 4G EPC core. Each NF in the control plane acts both as a service provider and as a service consumer. As a service provider, it may expose one or multiple NF services: all the NF services are accessed through the Service Based interface (SBI).

Each NF consuming a service can discover a suitable producer of a service instance through the Network Repository Function (NRF). The NRF supports service discovery by keeping a repository of all available NF instances and the services they expose. When deployed, the NF instance registers in the NRF its profile containing, among other relevant data, information regarding the services it provides and the binding information for accessing them.

The Network Exposure Function (NEF) may expose the services provided by the NFs inside the network to authorized external consumers such as the Applications Functions (AFs). The service framework groups support functions related to service registration, discovery, selection, and communication binding into a unified platform [4][5].

NF service producer and consumer can interact using two different models: the **request-response model** and the **subscribe-notify model**. In the first model, the service consumer sends a request message to the target service provider that sends its response message back. In the second model, the service consumer first subscribes with the provider to an NF service for a (set of) certain event(s) set. The service consumer will then receive a notification message from the service producer whenever a subscribed event occurs.

Figure 10 SBI request-response model and subscribe-notify model

Service Communication Proxy (SCP) introduced in Release 16 is a functionality similar to the Diameter Routing Agent (DRA) in 4G. It serves as a central control point in the signalling network

core. It performs multiple key functions, simplifying the core network routing topology and offloading the Network Repository Function (NRF) from service discovery, thus enabling greater 5G core network geo-distributed scalability.

Communication within the 5GC

In 5GC, 3GPP has taken advantage of **NFV (Network functions virtualization)**, and defined **Nodes as Functions** and Services that communicate universally through widely accepted and deployed protocols.

The 5GC communication is based on three main protocols:

GPRS Tunneling Protocol (GTP)

Used by the user plane for tunnelling the user plane traffic that carries subscriber traffic from the UE to the internet or subscriber services.

Packet Forwarding Control Protocol (PFCP)

Used for communicating between the control plane and the user plane gateway functions.

Hypertext Transfer Protocol version 2 (HTTP/2) on top of TLS/TCP

Used by the control plane SBI to register, establish, manage and tear down user devices/sessions. NFs uses HTTP/2 as described in IETF RFC 7540 in combination REST-style API and JSON, as the application layer serialization protocol, on top of TLS/TCP as the transport protocol. Since HTTP/2 is run on top of TLS, the traffic is encrypted, and no traditional packet inspection is possible.

The emerging transport protocol QUIC (Quick UDP Internet Connections) is considered a replacement of TCP/TLS connections, and it is under development by IETF (now in Version 1). HTTP/3 is the mapping of HTTP to QUIC and is the QPACK header compression scheme. QUIC is being considered as the way toward HTTP/3 for supporting SBI communications.

Figure 11 - Network stack

In the **5GC SBI (Service Based Interface) APIs**, A URI (Universal Resource Identifier) uniquely identifies a resource and structure is as below:

```
{apiRoot}/{apiName}/{apiVersion}/{apiSpecificResourceUriPart}
```

Aspects of the SBA and SBI relevant for monitoring

SBA is heavily based on virtualization. The virtual network functions (VNFs) require lightweight monitoring solutions to provide the context of the service chain and subscriber session, optimize performance, get end-to-end visibility of services (voice over IP, Internet of Things, network slices, etc.), and deliver QoS/SLA.

Multiple layers are present in the 5G infrastructure: e.g. the NFV infrastructure, the various virtual infrastructure managers or VIMs (OpenStack, Kubernetes, etc.), VNF managers, and the VNF applications themselves. 5G requires the monitoring and the correlation of performance data to be done across all these layers. To achieve this goal, it could be necessary to collect data from new sources such as servers, hypervisors, containers, and VNF vendor-specific application programming interfaces (APIs).

Visibility into a UE's traffic requires understanding the subscriber attributes. The stateful information contained within HTTP/2 and PFCP needs to be exploited to correlate the various subscriber-specific user sessions carried within the GTP tunnel and provide monitoring tools an accurate view of each subscriber's traffic on the network.

The 5GC SBI adopts TLS encryption by default. This complicates, if not impedes, the monitoring; therefore, passive probing is no longer effective. Alternative collect data means are needed, such as monitoring through event-based feeds provided by NFs or SSL description tools.

Currently, the SBA is applied only to the control plane of the 5G core network. However, the cloud-native design principle is expected to be applied in a broader scope in the future 6G

networks. For example, the SBA framework could be extended to an end-to-end architecture that comprises multiple planes, including the data, control, and application planes as defined in the SDN architecture, and across multiple domains, including the access, transport, and core networks.

Edge Computing and Multiaccess Edge Computing (MEC)

Edge Computing is an important introduction to 5G. It allows the 5G networks to achieve the latency requirements of URLLC use cases, but it also has other applications and benefits. Even if the edge cloud is often pictured near the gNodeB, different deployments are possible. Depending on its position in the infrastructure, the Edge Cloud can be referred to as Far Edge, Near Edge, or Central Office Edge. This terminology is commonly used for indicating such deployment options.

Thanks to the SBA and CUPS, Edge Computing is natively supported in 3GPP.

Standardization aspects

The ETSI MEC architecture is the emerging edge computing paradigm that essentially deploys decentralized cloud computing capabilities in the network infrastructures, typically at the network edge [6]. Even if Edge Cloud is defined inside the 3GPP standard, it has strong synergies with the ETSI MEC framework. The synergized architecture shown in the figure below has been proposed in [10].

Figure 12 Proposed Synergized architecture leveraging ETSI ISG MEC and 3GPP Specifications, as from June 2020 [10]

As the 5GC, also the Edge leverage on a cloud-native network design and adopts the virtualization and service-oriented architecture, facilitating the convergence between networking and

cloud/edge computing and going towards integrated management of networking-computing functionalities and unified provisioning of network and cloud/edge services [11].

In MEC-in NFV reference architecture, a unified virtualization layer for network-compute infrastructures and common virtual network/compute functions management is proposed. MEC and SBA share similar approaches about network function interactions, system operations, and service provisioning shared with cloud and edge computing [12][9].

The MEC architecture brings edge cloud near the access networks, providing capabilities to facilitate the development of edge applications that fully take advantage of the edge location and capabilities. It also provides the reference architecture for application orchestration.

The MEC host is at the core of the architecture and contains the MEC platform (MECP). This platform is built on top of the virtualized network-compute infrastructure, and various MEC applications can be deployed on the platform. The true impact of the edge computing paradigm relies on its interaction with networking. Going in this direction, ETSI MEC introduces various Service APIs to support the development of applications at the network Edge (or edge aware applications). Plus, it provides mechanisms for the migration of edge applications in case of handover. The MEC Apis natively provided as services by MECP to the Apps derive from the availability of access network information. These include location services, RNIS services, V2X services. Services can also be provided to the MEC application by other MEC apps, with the intermediation of the MECP.

The MECP Manager (MECP-M) manages the infrastructure, platform, and MEC applications at the host level. The MEC orchestrator (or MEO) is at the core of system-level management. It maintains a global view of the entire MEC system for coordinating host management for end-to-end service provisioning [7].

ETSI MEC ISG has also developed a reference architecture, called MEC-in-NFV, for deploying MEC in an NFV environment [8]. MEC-in-NFV shows how MEC entities can be integrated into the NFV architecture, fully leveraging NFV MANO capabilities: the MEC platform and MEC applications are managed by NFV MANO as regular VNFs. This approach allows leveraging NFV MANO for unified management and orchestration of both VNFs and MEC applications.

One of the key points of implementing Edge computing is the capability of steering the traffic towards the edge host. In 5G, this is done by instantiating a UPF by the Edge host. The UPF can terminate the GTP-U traffic and route it towards the destination Edge Application. This deployment can be done statically or dynamically, depending on the requirements. The capability to redefine traffic rules dynamically is essential in the user mobility context for maintaining the client connection to the service. User application context can be migrated to an edge near the user while he is moving. The user traffic needs to be redirected to the relocated service instance to maintain the QoS. Various implementation options exist and can also involve redirection through DNS reconfiguration. The UPF can be reconfigured by the MECP leveraging the SBI.

Depending on the level of trust, reconfiguration can be done either directly or through the intermediation of the NEF.

Aspects of Edge Computing and MEC relevant for monitoring

The convergence of the network cloud/edge with integrated network-compute infrastructures is expected to be a key feature of future networks. It will allow end-to-end provisioning of composite network-cloud/edge services with a high degree of automation. The adoption of cloud-native network design facilitates convergence between networking and cloud/edge computing. Being able to capture the correct monitoring metrics will be necessary to optimise resource utilization and service performance [9].

Being services no longer concentrated in a centralized data centre, but on highly distributed nodes, also monitoring activities should take into account this architecture:

- Points of termination of the GTP tunnels carrying data traffic are distributed across the edge nodes of the network. Data is consumed and generated at the edge.
- Services are provisioned over virtualized infrastructure with limited resources that need to be monitored for optimal utilization. Applications at the edge may be dynamically deployed and un-deployed, as needed.
- Also traffic rules may be dynamic, diverging traffic to the edge, and user traffic data path can vary over time to follow application needs.

5G Network Slicing

Network slicing is the concept of creating multiple virtual networks on a shared physical infrastructure associated with specific SLAs. In 5G, Network Slicing provides support to demanding network services such as enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC), massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC), and Vehicle to Everything (V2X). Each of them has specific throughput, latency, and reliability requirements. These can be fulfilled by creating tailored multiple logical networks that are created on top of a common physical infrastructure: i.e., the Radio Access Network (RAN), the Core Network (CN), and the Transport Network (TN).

Network slicing is not new, but its concept has been greatly expanded in 5G with new slicing. Since the early stages of 5G SA standardization work in 3GPP in 2017, many requirements from various vertical industries have been requested to be included as 5G standard requirements. At those early stages, network slicing had quite limited support. 4G slicing could be partially implemented by network-sharing technology but with limitations. Solutions were mostly addressing service isolation within a common infrastructure that could be achieved with methods like Access Point Name (APN) Routing, Multi Operator Core Network (MOCN), and Dedicated Core Network (DECOR).

In 3GPP Release 16, various vertical features have been defined (such as Time Sensitive Network (TSN), Virtual Network (VN), Non Public Network (NPN), URLLC, V2X and Cellular IoTs) targeting lower latency, reliable data transmission, higher data rates and industry specific features. Network slicing became prominent as it is a key capability to enable flexibility in the network, as it allows multiple logical networks to be created.

In 5G, network slicing is provided natively. It allows creating virtual data pipelines for each data type service through End-to-End (E2E) service orchestration, thus assuring the QoS for each service. Each slice can provide a complete set of network functionalities, including RAN functions and core NFs [31]. For creating and managing different sliced virtual networks, a collection of platform/systems and well-designed mechanism or tools are needed. Between then, E2E network slicing management and automation is fundamental to ensure efficiency, flexibility and stable operation.

Standardization aspects

Thanks to the maturity achieved by various state-of-the-art technologies, the efforts from standardization groups and the open-source community, network slicing is now possible. Multiple SDOs have been working in the definition and scope of the network slicing architecture, as well as on the specification of its various components. The first 5G network slicing concept and its high-level architecture has been proposed by the NGMN (Next Generation Mobile Networks) Alliance [28][29]. The 3GPP standardization process by 3GPP (mainly conducted by SA2/SA3/SA5 working groups) was first focalized on the core side and then extended to the RAN, Transport and End-to-End management. Major updates related to slicing are reported to the following 3GPP standardization documents:

- 3GPP TS 23.501~502, System architecture for the 5G
- 3GPP TS 23.530~533 Management & orchestration of network slicing
- 3GPP TR 28.801~805 Study on management & orchestration of network slicing

The ETSI work on NFV architectural framework definition, and information model was fundamental for supporting End-to-End (E2E) service orchestration in network slicing.

Network slicing implementation is also based on Software Defined Network (SDN). From an SDN standpoint, Open Network Foundation (ONF), which introduced OpenFlow for SDN, defined the methods to apply SDN architecture to 5G slicing [30].

The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) has contributed a rich set of control plane protocols (e.g., NETCONF/RESTCONF/ PCEP/BGP-LS, etc.), data plane protocols (e.g., SRv6, SR-MPLS, etc.) and various YANG data models (e.g., ACTN VN, L1/2/3 Service Models, TE/Tunnel Models, etc.) to support transport network slicing

Core, Access and Transport Network Slicing Architecture

Multiple layers should be considered when providing an E2E network slicing, which may refer to different standardization initiatives. The 3GPP reference architecture provides slice related functionalities associated with CN and RAN. However, also non-3GPP components are involved in slicing, e.g., the transport network (TN) and the Data Center (DC) network:

- In the 5GC, some of the NFs can be shared between network slices, while others are deployed only for a specific service within a sliced network.
- For the RAN slicing, it is possible to leverage the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) (defined by O-RAN) as a component for quick policy application and real-time control.
- The TN provides slicing related functions between sets of connection points in the networks such as Front, Mid and Backhaul. The TN orchestration can manage/control resources for the slicing of transport domains and coordinate actions across domains such as IP or Optical domains through multilayer path computation and optimization [32][33].

Managing and Identifying Network Slices by URSP and S-NSSAIs

The main difference in network slice selection between 4G and 5G Networks is that while in 5G network, slice selection policy can be configured dynamically, in 4G slice selection policy is pre-defined and cannot be changed dynamically in 4G network. This staticity makes it nearly impossible to install new services in the network for a UE in 4G.

To enable dynamicity, 5G introduces the UE route selection policy (URSP). It is included in the UE policies (along with the Access network discovery and selection policy, ANDSP) and allows to manage network slice's information for the UE. It is a network slice feature enabled by the PCF, which informs the network slice status to the UE via the AMF. Through the URSP feature, 5G network operators can easily configure new services for a UE. The UE policies can be delivered from the PCF to the UE.

The URSP contains various valuable information for the application and network slice mapping: the Application Descriptors, the Single-Network Slice Selection Assistance Information (S-NSSAI), the Data Network Name (DNN), the Session and Service Continuity (SSC) mode.

The S-NSSAI identifies each network slice service. An S-NSSAI is composed of two parts:

- A Slice/Service type (SST), an 8bits number, which refers to the expected network slice behaviour in terms of features and services; SST field value can be standardized (3GPP defined 0 to 127) or non-standardized (Operator-Reserved 128 to 255). SST values are standardized for slices suitable for handling: 5G enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable low latency communications (URLLC), massive IoT (MIoT), and V2X services (V2X).

- A Slice Differentiator (SD or SST-SD), a 24bits number, contains optional information complementing the Slice/Service type(s). It is used to differentiate amongst multiple network slices of the same Slice/Service type. The Slice Differentiator (SD) field can be used to build customized network slices: it can be used to describe services, customer information and priority

Analytics-based Network Slice Optimization

Network slice instances (NSI) share a common physical infrastructure and its resources. Resource requirements for each slice vary because of mixed traffic classes with different QoS requirements and various SLAs with different parameters. Automation is one of the key functionalities unlocking the potential of network slices, allowing a more granular level of management that take full advantage of a cloud-native, fully virtualized network. A network slice is dynamic and flexible, meaning it can be easily created and destroyed on demand: a network slice could be very dynamic and perhaps last for only five minutes, which makes resource optimization fundamental for the efficient use of scarce resources (e.g., resource blocks in RAN, bandwidth in TN, number of VMs or containers, or overall computing resources).

Auto-scaling of NSI resources is needed to meet the service requirement of slice customers, as well as to use scarce resources efficiently. Therefore, monitoring and storing NSI performance data during its lifecycle is needed. Based on historical data and experience, artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques can be utilized to predict service key performance indicators (KPI), service health state, and resource usage to spot possible failures and risks in advance.

For instance, a sudden increase in traffic load and network congestion can be expected in festivals, sports events, or holidays. NSI resource optimizer predicts the performance degradation and makes a decision to scale out the NSI in advance. Consequently, more resources are allocated to accommodate the increased traffic and number of UEs for preserving QoE and avoiding network congestion while minimizing the impact on traffic and services in other NSIs in the same network. On the contrary, NSIs can be scaled down to allocate resources for other slices when the traffic load decreases or can be configured to accommodate more UEs in the slice.

The NWDAF provides load level information for a network slice, collects and analyzes the aggregated data per slice and aids in network optimization. The Network Slice Selection Function (NSSF) and the Policy Control Function (PCF) are potential "consumers" of the NWDAF. The NWDAF could provide an essential part of this drive to automate network slice management.

Aspects of 5G Slicing relevant for monitoring

5G allows complete end-to-end (E2E) slicing to serve multiple business purposes. Each Network Slice Instance has to guarantee specific service-level agreements (SLAs), depending on its own profile (service classes or custom). In order to do this, per-slice traffic metrics and performance

(e.g., data rate, packet drop, and latency) are needed, as well as metrics such as end users' geographical distribution. Per session, user and slice instance-based monitoring may be required.

Network slice monitoring is one of the most critical capabilities for CSP together with unified performance management. Unified performance management reflects the need for holistic monitoring of a network that supports a hybrid physical layer (3G/4G/5G, WiFi) and that leverages network functions virtualization (NFV) cloud infrastructure still supporting traditional network functions. Network slice monitoring relevance reflects the challenge of assuring that virtual resources assigned to specific applications or customers will meet the required service levels. In slicing, network and computing resources can be partitioned logically for individual customers or applications. In 5G network, the slice selection policy can be configured dynamically through URSP, while the slice selection policy is pre-defined and cannot be changed dynamically in the 4G network.

Monitoring traffic characteristics and performance (e.g., data rate, packet drop, and latency), the end user's geographical distribution, per session/user/slice instance-based monitoring, and more will be key to the success of network slicing.

For a typical network slicing architecture, key characteristics of cross-layer architecture include:

1. A Cloud Orchestration framework that oversees network slice capacity, qualification, SLA, and network health monitoring;
2. Domain Resource Orchestration provides LCM (life cycle management). It reserves, assigns, scales, and controls the network functions for computing, storage and network resources per RAN, TN, and CN domain. The orchestrator can manage resources with the VIMs through their northbound APIs;
3. Near-RT RIC performs RAN slicing optimization based on real-time monitoring and control of RAN data.
4. Distributed Unit (DU), Centralized Unit - Control Plane (CU-CP), and Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) are typically shared by several network slices.
5. CU-UP, Session Management Function (SMF) and User Plane Function (UPF) are typically dedicated to particular network slices.
6. User Data Management (UDM) and Network Slice Selection Function (NSSF) are shared by all network slices.
7. Network Repository Function (NRF) and Policy Control Function (PCF) can be common or network slice specific. The slice configured by the SLA provides isolated services for each divided bearer path (DU, CU-UP, UPF, and DN).

Data Analytics Functions (NWDAFs)

The 5GC Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) provides network data collection and analytics, enabling closed-loop optimization, network automation and service orchestration.

NWDAF is designed to acquire data from 5GC NFs, and expose analytic services on the SBIs for seamless integration with the rest of the NFs and the operator's cloud environment. [14].

The Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) has been introduced in TS 29.5201 as part of Core (5GC) for supporting intelligent and autonomous network operations and service management [12]. It is an evolution of the RAN Congestion Awareness Function (RCAF) from previous 3GPP releases. It provides centralized data collection/analytics.

NWDAF has been briefly outlined in the 3GPP Release-15 specifications, while the more detailed functionalities were defined as part of Release-16 work.

The NWDAF is a general system module in the 5G architecture. It allows various data-driven AI/ML-based analytics technologies to be integrated with 5G networks. The figure below shows a general framework for NWDAF-based 5G network automation: the NWDAF collects data from various NFs and AFs (using event exposure services offered by them) in the 5G system for performing the analytics. The uses as data sources also subscriber-related data from UDR repositories and data from the Operation, Administration, and Management (OAM) system. The NWDAF elaborates this data and produces analytics information that is to the NFs/AFs that made the request. NFs and AFs leverage such information for making decisions about network operations and management actions. The NWDAF also exposes analytics information to the OAM.

The analytics results obtained by NWDAF can be consumed by: (i) operators in various operational tasks; (ii) by other NFs to control communications; (ii) and by external applications, leveraging on the NEF (Network Exposure Function). NWDAF has 3GPP defined standard interfaces using which NFs can request analytics information.

Figure 13 Network Data Analytics Function (TS 29.520) [13]

Standardization aspects

NWDAF was first introduced in Rel 15 but did not see much adoption at the time. This is because of the unavailability of data and the specifications in 3GPP not being fully defined for NWDAF. With 5G deployments taking off and the completion of the necessary 3GPP specifications, there is a growing interest in NWDAF adoption.

The architecture of NWDAF is defined in 3GPP Specifications TS 23.288, and the detailed specification with APIs is defined in 3GPP Specification TS 29.520. Release 17 added further details to NWDAF, defining two separate NWDAF functions, the Analytics Logical Function (AnLF) and the Model Training Logical Function (MTLF), going towards the MLOPS operations.

NWDAF Analytics and Use Cases

The NWDAF collects continuously network data from the NFs, performs statistical or predictive analytics on it (utilizing, e.g., AI/ML algorithms), and provides real-time analytics back to the NFs and the operator's BSS/OSS systems. The output from NWDAF ranges from data and statistics to predictions that can use machine learning (ML) models. AI and ML can forecast resource utilization trends and proactively improve/configure network resources. The automated, data-driven adjustments and insights provided by NWDAF are not possible through manual network monitoring.

NWDAF analytics can be used to constantly monitor the Service Experience, Network Conditions and Device Behavior metrics for the various types of 5G service. For example, it can be used to know how much users and applications are impacting the 5G network; how adverse network conditions are; or if an unusual device behaviour is impacting users and applications. NWDAF applications are quite broad: 3GPP defines many formula-based/AI-ML analytics in TR 23.791:

- Load level Computation and Prediction of a NSI
- Service Experience Computation and Prediction for an Application/UE group
- Load analytics information and Prediction for a specific NF
- Network Load Performance computation and future Load prediction
- Expected behaviour prediction for a group/specific UE
- Abnormal behaviour/Anomaly detection for a group/specific UE
- Mobility related information and prediction for a group/specific UE
- Communication pattern prediction for a specific UE
- Congestion information - Current and Predicted for a specific location;

Additionally, in Release 16, some additional NWDAF use cases have been added, such as 5G edge computing and Access Traffic Steering.

An Analytics Id identifies each use case. The Analytics Id based offering framework defined by 3GPP also allows to specify custom use cases, added to 3GPP standard defined ones (e.g., Operational Analytics for Customer Care, NOC and Subscriber Content Analytics for Targeted Marketing)

3GPP has defined 2 models to consume Analytics services from NWDAF.

1. Subscription model - in case periodic (or exceeding threshold notification) Analytics information is needed. Ex: Periodic Load information (current/predicted) of Network slice.
2. Request/Ad-Hoc model - if a one-time Analytics computation and information is needed. Ex: Experience score of a newly deployed Application for a particular day/hour/region.

Data collection

While services will run on the network, the NWDAF constantly monitors service quality and reacts to any network degradations. Network-related data can be collected from multiple sources, including: (i) standard data types from Network Functions (NFs) in the 5G Core, when the target data are related to individual User Equipment (UE) and network sessions; (ii) non-standard data from sources including Application Functions (AFs) and OAM layer functions, e.g., for data related to global network states, such as performance measurements of network slices and services/applications; (iii) non-standard data sources such as network probes.

The inclusion of the NWDAF as part of 5G Core makes interworking complexities simplified: NWDAF incorporates SBA standard interfaces to collect data by subscription or request model from other NFs and 5GC components. NWDAF provides with the ability to capture data from:

- non-SBI interfaces (N1, N2, N3, N4, N6, N9) and
- SBI interfaces (N5, N7, N8, N10, N11, N12, N13, N14, N15)

Analytics information is either statistical information of past events or predictive information. The types of observed events include:

- Slice load level information;
- Network slice instance load level information;
- Service experience;
- NF load;
- Network performance;
- Abnormal behaviour;
- UE mobility;
- UE communication;
- User data congestion; and

- QoS sustainability.

NWDAF deployment

NWDAF have a distributed architecture with multiple instances of NWDAF deployed in the 5G Core. Multiple NWDAF instances can be deployed as (i) a central NF, (ii) a collection of distributed NFs, (iii) a combination of both.

NWDAF instances do not need to provide the same type of analytics. It is possible to have NWDAF instances specialized in providing only some types of analytics. An analytics ID information element identifies the type of analytics that an NWDAF instance can generate, and a single NWDAF can provide multiple ids. The NWDAF is also associated with an Area of Interest, which is also the geographical location to which the NF belongs to.

Like other NFs, NWDAF registers itself with NRF (Network Repository Function) of the 5G Core, thus enabling analytics functions consumers to discover and select an NWDAF instance that is able to provide a specific type of analytics. Indeed, when an NWDAF instance registers itself at the NRF, it provides the list of analytics IDs that it supports as part of the NWDAF profile.

Monitoring related aspects

NWDAF retrieves events directly from the 5GC NF's event exposure interface. Events are created internally to the NFs when signalling procedures are processed per subscriber interaction. Examples of events are, e.g., when a subscriber moves to a new location initiating a New Radio (NR) handover: the information about this event is created per UE (User Equipment). It can be collected over the NWDAF Network Function Interface (Nnf) between the NWDAF and the NF.

Data collection may cause additional communication overheads between the NWDAF and other system modules, limiting system scalability and degrading network performance [1]. It is important to achieve a balance between the completeness/preciseness of the collected data and the overheads introduced by data collection. The NWDAF should be able to efficiently obtain the required data with an appropriate level of granularity. The following aspects of data collection are specified in the data retrieval request and subscription messages: granularity (individual event, a list of events, key performance indicators), temporality (periodical, on-demand by the NWDAF, triggered by specific criteria, with validity period), and individuality (aggregated data vs single scope data).

ETSI ENI - Experiential Networked Intelligence Architecture

ETSI ENI (Experiential Networked Intelligence) initiative defines standards for cognitive network management and helps implement 5G use cases based on environmental context and user requirements. The ISG ENI was launched in February 2017 by ETSI [17]. ENI is defined as “an

entity that provides intelligent network operation and management recommendations and/or commands to an assisted system (AS).” [61]

The ETSI ENI ISG have identified use cases in the areas of infrastructure management, network operation, service orchestration and management, and network assurance. As we can see, the ENI architecture may be applied to virtually all management aspects of future networks. [18]. When applied to 5G architecture, ETSI’s ENI provides a standardized approach for intelligently managing NSIs in a closed-loop system, enabling the automation and AI algorithms to configure NSIs in a scalable and flexible manner dynamically. For example, ENI architecture can be used to implement an intelligent network slice management strategy by applying machine learning (ML) to predict usage patterns, resource contentions, and developments.

A reference implementation of the ENI System, compliant with the architecture defined in ETSI GS ENI 005, comprises three main modules [17]:

- The **input processing module** contains (i) the data ingestion function, is responsible for collecting and processing the data acquired from multiple sources and preparing it for further processing and analysing by other ENI functions. Data is acquired in different formats and frequencies and (ii) the normalization function, which translates the data received from the ingestion function into a form that can be understood and used by other ENI functions. The data stream is converted to an ENI-defined format.;
- The **analysis module** gets as input an ENI-formatted stream and contains: (i) functions for knowledge management and processing (i.e., knowledge management, context-awareness, and cognition management functions); and (ii) functions for situation-aware model-driven policy generation (i.e. situation awareness, model-driven engineering, and policy management functions). These functions are at the core of an ENI system, performing real-time analytics to detect anomalies and determining if any actions need to be triggered for NSI reconfiguration. It can also do big data processing to prepare the data for training ML models.
- The **output generation module** comprises the denormalization function and the output generation functions. It may provide the business logic used to take actions based on triggered events, predefined policies, service and network current context, and ML inferences. The output generation module may be used to transform data to the consumer-desired format.

The API broker completes the architecture and provides a common communication channel between the ENI functions and the externally managed services. The ENI architecture therefore just needs to define a single API.

Figure 14 ETSI Experiential Networked Intelligent (ENI) architecture [17]

ETSI ENI architecture and 5G

The interaction between ENI and 5GC can be described in the following way. (1) Network elements from each NSI (e.g., UPF, SMF, PCF as well as common elements such as AMF, UDM, NSSF) send their network data to the ENI system: the sent data may include network triggers, slice utilization data, usage patterns, and other parameters. (2) The ENI system compares data received from network elements with the reference metadata to determine the current health of each network slice and analytics or ML algorithms to develop recommendations for NSIs. (3) The ENI system then sends the recommendations to the slice management and orchestration function (SMO). (4) The SMO function implements these recommendations on each NSI.

The ENI architecture for the management of vertical services and network slices in 5G network infrastructures can be implemented as an extended NFV MANO platform as a multi-layer ENI-assisted system. An example of such architecture has been demonstrated in the ESTI ENI PoC#9, entitled Autonomous Network Slice Management for 5G Vertical Services⁴ [62].

⁴ ETSI Wiki on POC09 Autonomous Network Slice Management for 5G Vertical Services: https://eniwiki.etsi.org/index.php?title=Poc_09:_Autonomous_Network_Slice_Management_for_5G_Vertical_Services

ETSI ENI Use Cases

ETSI ENI Use Cases has been defined in ETSI RGS/ENI-008 and are organized into four groups:

Network Operations

- Policy-driven IP managed networks
- Radio coverage and capacity optimization
- Intelligent software rollouts
- Policy-based network slicing for IoT security
- Intelligent fronthaul management and orchestration
- Elastic Resource Management and Orchestration
- Application Characteristic based Network Operation

Infrastructure Management

- Policy-driven IDC traffic steering
- Handling of peak planned occurrences
- Energy optimization using AI

Network Assurance

- Network fault identification and prediction
- Assurance of service requirements

Service Orchestration and Management

- Context-aware VoLTE service experience optimization
- Intelligent network slicing management
- Intelligent carrier-managed SD-WAN

Monitoring related aspects

The ETSI ENI Needs programmable and cross-layer monitoring to feed the ENI system with multi-source data, e.g., the consumption of virtual resources, application statistics and performance, service demands. It may need new probes to be dynamically installed and configured in virtual application functions or as additional network service elements. Due to the heterogeneous nature of data, dedicated exporters may be needed to normalize the data sent to the monitoring platform. It may require the adaptation of NFV Orchestration monitoring mechanisms to unify different metrics as input for the ENI system and allow dynamic monitoring configuration.

ITU-T FG-ML5G

The ITU-T Focus Group on ML for future networks, including 5G (FG-ML5G) has developed a unified architectural framework for both ML functionalities and network functions. [20]

The high-level structure of the ITU-T architecture for integrating ML in future networks comprises three subsystems [21]:

- **ML pipeline subsystem** is a set of logical nodes, each with specific functionalities, that combined form an ML application in the network. The chaining of these nodes represents the workflow of the information process in an ML application. The ML pipeline comprises:
 1. The Source (SRC) Node produces the input data consumed by the ML pipeline (e.g., UEs, SBA NFs such as SMF and AMF)
 2. The Collector (C) Node collects the data from various source nodes
 3. The Pre-Processor (PP) Node cleans, aggregates and prepares the data for the ML model
 4. The Model (M) Node, i.e. the ML model(s) used in the pipeline (e.g., a classification or prediction function).
 5. The Policy (P) Node applies policies to the output of the model node
 6. The Distributor (D) Node identifies the sink node(s) and distributes the output of the model node to the corresponding sink node(s).
 7. The Sink (SINK) Node, i.e. the target of the ML output on which it takes actions.
- **Management subsystem**, includes NFV MANO functions such as VIM, NFVM, and VNFO and extends the management and orchestration capabilities to ML pipeline nodes. Its core component is the MLFO (ML Function Orchestrator), responsible for managing and orchestrating the ML pipeline nodes. The MLFO selects the ML model node for each ML pipeline based on the ML intent⁵ and/or dynamic network conditions and model performance. ML pipeline nodes placement is based on the corresponding network capabilities and ML application constraints. The MLFO provides chaining functions to connect ML nodes together to form an ML pipeline.
- **ML sandbox subsystem**, an isolated domain meant to train, test, and evaluate ML pipelines before deploying them in a live network. Training and testing data can be simulated by the underlay network and/or collected from a live network. MLFO is also responsible for managing and monitoring the ML pipeline hosted in the sandbox. The sandbox subsystem allows ML pipelines to adapt to the dynamic networking environment in future networks.

⁵ The ML intent is a declarative description that can be used by the network operator to specify an ML application and the corresponding ML pipeline. [1].

An ML application can be realized by instantiating ML pipeline nodes as VNFs. The nodes are then associated with the technology-specific underlying NFs, based on the corresponding requirements of the ML application and the capabilities of the underlying network functions. This decomposition allows finer-grained modularity of the management system, which may enhance the flexibility and agility of network and service management.

Figure 15 ITU-T unified architecture for ML in future networks

ITU-T ML architecture and 5G

The ITU-T ML architecture is aligned with the 5G SBA as both embrace the cloud-native network design principle. Each ML pipeline node may be realized as an NF service as defined in 5G SBA, interacting with other nodes via the SBI. The ITU-T ML architecture may be realized based on the NWDAF/MDAS, e.g., an ML pipeline may have:

- the AMF as the SRC node;
- the PCF as the SINK node; and
- the other ML pipeline nodes hosted on the NWDAF.

The MFLO can compose ML pipeline nodes for constructing various ML applications, meeting diverse management requirements 5G network. Being able to orchestrate both the ML pipeline nodes and the network/compute functions in a unified architecture may greatly facilitate the seamless integration of ML techniques in 5G networks and support the network-cloud/edge convergence.

Monitoring related aspects

The ITU-T ML architecture defines specific reference points for handling data between the ML pipelines (including those hosted in the sandbox) and the underlay network. It also defines standard interfaces between each pair of subsystems, between the ML pipeline and the underlay network, between the ML sandbox and the simulated underlay networks. The SBI defined in the 5G SBA may be used to realise the interfaces between subsystems and the interfaces between ML pipeline nodes.

5G interfaces and functions relevant for monitoring

User Plane Function (UPF) defined in 3GPP Release 16 (R16)

The UPF was first introduced as an extension to existing Evolved Packet Cores (EPCs) by the 3GPP in their Release 14 specifications. It is part of the data plane evolution of a Control and User Plane Separation (CUPS) strategy. The control and user plane functions that were before delegated to the Packet Gateway (PGW) CUPS are decoupled, enabling the data forwarding component (PGW-U) to be decentralized. Packet processing and traffic aggregation can be decentralized and, e.g., performed closer to the network edge to increase bandwidth efficiencies while reducing network overload. The handling of the signalling traffic (PGW-C) remain in the core, northbound of the Mobility Management Entity (MME). The PGW function decoupling was first conceived to support early IoT applications and higher data rates. However, a complete implementation of control and user plane separation only provides a subset of the advantages adopting a 5G User Plane Function affords, such as network slicing. When deployed within a dynamic cloud-native compute infrastructure, the User Plane Function (UPF) delivers the packet processing foundation for Service Based Architectures (SBAs). [63]

The UPF is the interconnection point between the mobile infrastructure (the access network) and the Data Network (DN). It provides GPRS Tunneling Protocol encapsulation and decapsulation for the user plane (GTP-U). The PDU (Protocol Data Unit) session anchor point is the UPF and provides mobility within and between RATs (Radio Access Technologies), including sending one or more end marker packets to the gNB. The UPF provides packet routing and forwarding. It performs the role of an Uplink Classifier / UL-CL (directing flows to specific data networks based on traffic matching filters) and a Branching point, when acting as an Intermediate UPF (I-UPF) multi-homed to more than one PDU session anchor (PSA).

The UPF also performs application detection, using Service Data Flow (SDF) traffic filter templates or 3-tuple (protocol, server-side IP address and port number) Packet Flow Description (PFD) received from the SMF.

The UPF is able to perform per-flow QoS handling, including transport level packet marking for uplink (UL) and downlink (DL), rate limiting and reflective QoS (DSCP) marking on the DL.

Finally, it performs traffic usage reporting for billing and the Lawful Intercept (LI) collector interface.

The UPF has four distinct reference points:

- **N3**: Interface between the RAN (gNB) and the (initial) UPF.
- **N9**: Interface between two UPF's (i.e., the Intermediate I-UPF and the UPF Session Anchor)
- **N6**: Interface between the Data Network (DN) and the UPF

- **N4:** Interface between the Session Management Function (SMF) and the UPF

Figure 16 5G Core Reference Point Architecture ⁶

The protocol employed on the N3 and N9 interfaces **could** be the GPRS Tunneling Protocol (GTP) with header extensions for 5G, segment routing (SRv6 or NSH) or even an Information Centric Networking (ICN) protocol. The Locator/ID Separation data plane protocol (LISP-DP) over GTP or Identifier Locator Addressing (ILA) could also be utilized. A relay function would be performed by an I-UPF, while the UPF PDU Session Anchor would terminate these protocols.

⁶ From <https://www.metaswitch.com/hs-fs/hubfs/Blogs/multi-ran.png?width=2036&name=multi-ran.png>

Figure 17 5G User Plane Protocol Stack, employing STP with 5G header extensions

The UPF identifies user plane traffic flow based on information received from the SMF over the N4 reference point. The N4 interface employs the Packet Forwarding Control Protocol (PFCP), which was originally defined within 3GPP technical specification 29.244 for use on Sx reference points in support of CUPS. PFCP is similar to OpenFlow but can be limited to only the functionality required to support mobile networks. PFCP sessions, established with the UPF, define how packets are identified (Packet Detection Rule / PDR), forwarded (Forwarding Action Rules / FARs), processed (Buffering Action Rules / BARs), marked (QoS Enforcement Rules / QERs) and reported (Usage Reporting Rules / URRs).

Figure 18 Packet processing flow in the User Plane Function (per 3GPP TS29.244)

UPF can be implemented as a pure cloud-native network function. In order to achieve high packet throughputs with complex pipelines and low latencies, such components have historically been realized using dedicated hardware and custom silicon. Delivering a cloud-native UPF on shared resources demands solving complex real-time data processing problems and providing a high degree of flexibility in the pipeline to support emerging traffic tunnelling, mobility and infrastructure overlays. UPF instantiation must also be highly automated and orchestrated. This means developing or enhancing user-space data plane acceleration, runtime programmability techniques and tightly integrating with numerous cloud orchestration systems, such as Kubernetes.

The User Plane Function is a critical component for supporting the new generation of service-based architectures. The velocity of innovation in this area, however, should also allow the early majority of perspective CUPS adopters to adopt the UPF over interim PGW/SGW-U solutions, smoothing the migration from 4G to 5G.

MEC case and User Plane Function (UPF) interfaces

Significant reductions in both latency and backhaul traffic can be achieved by placing server applications and network functions at the network edge. However, this implies new challenges for their dynamic placement and management. The dynamic placement reconfiguration of 5G User Plane Functions (UPFs) in a MEC ecosystem is required to adapt to changes in user locations while ensuring QoS and network operator expenditures reduction. To determine the optimal UPF placement configuration (e.g., number of UPFs and user-UPF mapping), optimizations solutions (like Integer Linear Programming (ILP)) are required. By considering several cost components along with service requirements.

Network Slicing interfaces

Network slicing is end-to-end, including RAN and Transport network, but it also crosses multi-access, multi-domain networks and could very likely be a multi-operator domain. This E2E-NSI will be deployed by selecting or instantiating a combination of access, fixed and mobile, for transport and core subnetworks.

The edge and core network is composed of the 3GPP 5G Core User plane PNF (UPF) and control plane VNF (AMF, UDM, AUSF, for example) placed appropriately at the edge, or in the core, depending on placement policy or latency requirements.

Study on orchestration techniques for virtualized monitoring platforms.

To gain visibility and meaningful insight into the state of a 5G system, the monitoring systems need to process huge datasets of complex information. It includes building a well-defined system of measurement points to collect data able to verify the intended behaviour of 5G entities and quickly notify if there is any drift from the regular behaviour.

The 5G SBA leverages a virtualized infrastructure (NFVI). Hardware middleboxes are substituted with software entities, i.e., Virtualized Network Functions (VNF). VNF instances can be virtual machines or containers and are hosted by industry-standard Physical Nodes (PNs) such as routers, switches, and commodity servers (commercial off-the-shelf hardware). Multiple VNFs can share the same PN, and one VNF can be scaled to accommodate increased demand, being its replicas instantiated on multiple PNs.

Maintaining the same level of reliability and availability when moving Physical Network Functions (PNFs) to Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) is challenging. A PNF provides a tight integration that includes all necessary software and services, purpose-built to its specific function. The risk is very low that an integration issue will impact the performance of a PNF. In the case of VNFs and CNFs, hardware and software are separately developed. Since a VNF is provided independent of hardware, it requires that both the host infrastructure and the VNF are qualified independently, then correlated to assess performance and identify faults.

Unlike PNFs and their accompanying defined specifications, VNFs do not have identified performance caps as applied to infrastructure [56]. This presents a challenge to defining performance thresholds for fault management related to infrastructure that is not yet being heavily utilized. Benchmarking tools in place of VNFs are applicable to assessing the performance of physical, virtualized and Cloud-Native infrastructures. Benchmarking provides the ability to characterize VNF work-load performance metrics to assist with optimizing the assigned infrastructure resources for VNF deployment as well as define infrastructure performance monitoring and alert thresholds. Furthermore, benchmarking can deliver better capacity planning for VNFs that auto-scale and for VNFs that are sensitive to latencies from remote peers, network-attached services, and storage [57].

In 5G, various verticals use cases can be present simultaneously thanks to network slicing techniques that provide dedicated and isolated services over a common physical infrastructure but with their own set of requirements. Usually, slices have associated a set of requirements that follow the corresponding vertical Service Level Agreement (SLA).

Mechanisms like service assurance (SA) are put in place to assure that SLAs are guaranteed. Assuring the SLA of multiple slices with diverging requirements at the same time is a big challenge compared to the existing service assurance (SA) in legacy networks. For this reason, automating the slice provisioning process is mandatory. SA includes both the monitoring of network operations and service performance and the processing and analyzing the monitoring data (analytics). Thanks to the outcomes of the SA, it is possible to take corrective actions and resolve SLA issues through orchestration and management operations. The combination of SA, orchestration, and management for the closed-loop of the service provisioning automation.

Orchestration consists in effectively coordinating the deployment of a set of virtualized services, properly allocating resources, and deciding where to place VNFs across available PNF nodes [58]. Orchestration is a key feature of the Cloud Computing model. It allows to fully exploits its benefits while fulfilling operational and quality objectives of end-users and Cloud providers and efficiently exploiting the available resources. Orchestration is usually supported by the SA (Monitoring and Analytics) set of functionalities.

A network slice is hierarchically constructed by multiple components [57], being compound by various layers: infrastructure, Network Functions (NFs, including virtualized network function (VNF) and physical network functions (PNF)), network service (NS), and E2E Slice layer. Also, the

Management and Orchestration of Network Slicing (MONS) follows a similar hierarchy, adding to traditional orchestration additional components to support the entire slice end to end (E2E) orchestration [58].

Accordingly, SA architecture is designed in a similar way. Monitoring data can come from different levels: E2E service monitoring, Network Service (NS) monitoring, Network Function (NF) monitoring, or Infrastructure monitoring. To each of these levels, an analogous analytic function corresponds. The correlation of the results of the analysis of the data collected from all the levels is also possible.

VNFs can be placed dynamically by the orchestrator to provide a specific network service (NS). A set of VNFs can be chained to create a Service Function Chain (SFC), also known as a VNF forwarding graph. The SFC is chained in a specific order to provide a specific service to the customer. VNFs are then placed on PNs, and virtual links are created to create the SFC (Fig1.)

Figure 19 SFC example

Service Level Agreements (SLAs) are usually imposed on services created in this way. SLAs include measures such as minimum latency involved in getting a service, minimum bandwidth consumption while creating the SFC, or the maximum data rate while running the application. VNF placement has a crucial role in guaranteeing that services meet their SLAs. Indeed, if the VNFs are not correctly placed in the network, the created SFCs may not be able to meet the required SLAs.

The monitoring system ensures that the NS and its SFC composing VNFs operate correctly and meet their SLAs. The network-related information collected includes various statistical data,

traffic-related information, profiles of related application scenarios, and information about data packets and their corresponding samples. Collected data allows to properly estimate the network conditions for further monitoring (e.g., anomaly detection, traffic estimation, and various network maintenance-related activities) and decision-making.

The management of Monitoring Services in a 5G infrastructure is hard to perform due to the huge number of 5G devices consuming network services, the high mobility of these devices, the bandwidth and latency of future mobile communications, and the presence of slicing, among others. At the same time, it is a critical service consumed by the network automation to guarantee the SLAs of services and slices. The best deployment at a given time depends on the current topology and requirements. The orchestration of monitoring services becomes then a critical and complex process that should be carried out in an automatic way.

Figure 20 Monitoring and orchestration solutions applied over the 5G network data plane

Virtual probes need to be considered during orchestration to deploy a monitored 5G Core network slice. Even if this can be done after SFC is placed, jointly orchestrating NFs and monitoring system virtual components can improve performance. The problem of embedding (i.e., VNF placement and chaining problem) such kind of architectures within a given Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure (NFV-I) depends on how the Monitoring System is architecture. Different approaches have different effects on how NF are orchestrated. The main requirement remains to capture the traffic between two given VNFs or CNFs without impacting network performance. Monitoring in virtualized environments has some characteristics that need to be considered while orchestrating SFCs.

Figure 21 Selection of SA monitoring solutions [60]

There diverse monitoring solutions are offered by vendors (Fig. 11) [60].

Virtualized Infrastructure Managers (VIM) are equipped with telemetry tools to monitor infrastructure at the infrastructure level. Examples are OpenStack's Ceilometer, Gnocchi or Aodh, and VMWare vCloud. OpenDaylight (ODL) statistics manager monitors the SDN infrastructure.

At the VNF layer, built-in monitoring functions are used. Examples are the VNF Event Stream (VES) agent and the VNF Manager (VNFM), which monitor VNFs. EMS is used to manage physical network functions (PNF). Besides, Open Source MANO (OSM) recently added a monitoring function for infrastructure and VNFs.

At the NS and slice service layer, external monitoring tools are used to measure the performance of an NS within a domain or an E2E slice actively (active virtual probes (vProbe)), passively (passive vTap) or hybrid [3].

Quality of experience (QoE) monitoring is brought into the framework to provide insight into how end-users perceive the slice service. Two basic approaches can be used to collect data from 5G infrastructure, applications, and cloud environment: use an agent or a collector (i.e., a Virtual Monitoring Function, vMF), or instrument the Network Functions to send telemetry data.

[60] provides an interesting analysis, and solutions, on the interrelation between monitoring and analytics.

In [40], three different solutions are listed:

- Agent Based Architecture (ABA) - that not all VNF providers/vendors are willing to have a third-party software plugged within their VMs that packages their proprietary systems. Besides, this architecture generates the same amount of a given traffic.
- Mirroring Based Architecture (MBA). Agent Free Architecture (TAP as a service) **vPort** mirroring is supported by some VIMs and SDN controllers. Transparent to the VMs
- Chaining Based Architecture (No-vPB) vProbe Chaining (without vPB Scheme)

In Agent Based Architecture (ABA) architecture, each one of the VMs transiting a traffic that should be monitored, is instrumented with an **agent** that can be a vTap that mirrors the traffic to the vPacket-Broker or a vProbe that produces telemetry data. Each agent within a VMF is responsible for resending the traffic to the vPacket-Broker. This architecture generates the same amount of a given traffic, and there is no optimization in the mirroring process. So, the network can be rapidly overloaded by the mirrored traffic that will affect and degrade the network's performance. The agent also increases the computing requirements of the VNF, which may need to scale out to meet the demand.

Figure 22 Agent Based Architecture (ABA)

vProbe can be part of a generic 5G Network Function (5G NF). For example, its functionality can be to analyze the multimedia content passing through it and to provide a measure of Quality of Experience (QoE). In this case, the vProbe network function aims to measure the QoE based on the media content that the platform is providing to the end-user.

In Mirroring Based Architecture (MBA), vPort mirroring mechanism is used to replicate traffic supported by some Virtual Infrastructure Managers (VIMs). VIMs like VMware, OpenStack and some SDN controllers provide some kind of functionality for traffic mirroring. VMware supports it within the switch, and OpenStack provides Tap as a Service (TaaS) module. Those mechanisms are transparent to the VMs. The VIM networking module ensures the port mirroring on the virtual switches and compute resources and offloads the VMs from ensuring extra tasks rather than their main functionalities. This monitoring is therefore done at the NFVI level, and resource consuming should be treated as such.

Figure 23 Mirroring Based Architecture (MBA)

In Chaining Based Architecture, note that a vPacket Broker is not used. In fact, a vProbe is inserted between each couple of VMs to monitor their exchanged traffic flows. This assumes that the traditional routines performed by a PacketBroker, like filtering based on some criteria, will be ensured by the vProbe or the smartNICs. In this context, we are not interested in the aggregation capabilities of the vPB to be supported by the vProbe because there is no need to aggregate flows since we are considering only one flow. A new vProbe will be considered for each link to be monitored in this architecture. The smart NICs are able to realize some filtering mechanisms so they can stop the reception of some packets and keep only the ones needed by the vProbe to be analyzed and monitored. In Fig. 4, we represent this vPB free architecture.

Figure 24 Chaining Based Architecture

When using an agent or a collector, network taps and probes are virtualized in Virtual Monitoring Functions (vMFs). vProbe and vPacket-Broker (vPB) deployment schemes within a slice allow a network operator to meet the monitoring need and have full network visibility. As such, they need to be embedded into the NF business logic. Once the vMFs are deployed on top of the PNs, most of the processed and unprocessed data packets pass through the vMFs for monitoring purposes (Fig.2).

5G Networks relays of the use of vertical slices and are expected to have a highly dynamic topology and demands. Mobility and edge computing add complexity to the scenario. There is need to dynamically deploy virtualized network services on-demand. Like the other components of the 5G network, the deployment of vProbes and vPacket Brokers should also be automated and simultaneously considered in 5GC slices instantiations and deployments.

Figure 25 Placement of vMFs

vMFs compete for the same resources of Applications and Network Functions, and their inclusion incurs additional E2E Transmission Delay (ETD). To mitigate the ETD in the softwarized SFCs, proximal placement of the vMFs is to be exercised. Figure 1 shows an example of softwarized 5G architecture which consists of the underlay PN network and the overlay networks of the VNFs and a few vMFs.

vMFs placement is crucial to run virtualized monitoring without affecting services operations and avoid VNFs or service degradation. Wise placement location of vMFs can reduce the communication delay between the deployed VNF and vMF and the number of required vMFs.

SFC Placement

The VNF placement and chaining problem can be performed considering different goals. For example, the goal can be that of minimizing operational cost [41][42]. In this case, the problem will consider deployment, energy, communication, traffic forwarding, and resource

fragmentation costs, subject to, e.g., performance constraints. Also, minimization of the total energy [43] or the cost of the total number of physical servers and links used for provisioning services [44] can be set as goals of the SFC placement problem. Typical problems like those above are mainly focused on i) minimizing capital and operational costs by minimizing resource consumption and ii) maximizing revenue for network operators by offering new services dynamically in the same network infrastructure.

Reliability-aware SFC placement takes into account VNF failures and can target various goals, such as minimizing the total bandwidth usage [45], the total resource usage cost [46][47] (including physical servers and physical links costs), or the number of servers used [48]. Reliability-aware and resource-efficient SFC placement can also consider as a goal for CAPEX and OPEX reduction (as in [49]). Latency-aware SFC placement, instead, considers latency constraints typical of, e.g., URLLC services. Again, they can target different goals, such as minimizing overall power consumption, including physical servers and switches power consumption [50], or delay including inter VNF and inter-server communication delays [51].

When considering vMFs placement, processing delay of VNFs, their reliability, and monitoring aspects should be considered.

Monitoring Function Placement

Network dynamics and stringent SLA objectives require monitoring the network closely to meet the various dynamic requirements with minimal network resources.

One approach is to deploy vMFs on the SFCs already deployed and consider the SFC placement and monitoring function placement separately. In this case, it is assumed that VNFs of SFCs are already reliably deployed in the network and satisfy users' requirements. The paths of SFCs are known for the monitoring functions to be placed.

Orchestration can have as a target goal, e.g., to minimize the number of probes placed to monitor multiple SFCs [51]. However, the on-demand monitoring function deployment approach may not be resource efficient if the number of probes is the only discriminant (there are no criteria with which they are placed) [52]. The goal can be set to maximise both network and computing resource utilization [53], minimise the number of deployed vMFs and forward the cost of monitoring flows [54]. Solutions in [53] and [54] are not scalable, and SFC placement and reliability of monitoring functions are not considered.

In many cases, vMF is placed with network security monitoring in mind [55]. They are placed, e.g., in NFV-enabled data centres to address the issue of insider security attacks by watching communications between pairs of virtual machines to minimize the number of monitoring VNFs deployed.

Monitoring functions (vMFs) play a significant role in network and service automation, especially when making quick decisions is required to meet SLAs. Decisions regarding when to scale or migrate a VNF, or timely reroute traffic upon the identification of faults, VNF interference, and performance degradation are made based on the analysis results of traffic collected by vMF nodes. The capacity of continuous monitoring of the network and the reliability of the vMF nodes have thus an impact in assuring the service continuity.

vMF placement depends on the placement details of SFCs and on network topology information; therefore, the placement of the VNFs of an SFC and a vMFs monitoring can be considered a joint problem.

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Annex:

Service Based Architecture SBA Functions Reference

Figure 26 Service Based Architecture SBA Functions Reference [64]

The Control Plane – AMF and SMF - The Mobility Management Entity (MME) in LTE is the signalling node for UE access and mobility, establishing the bearer path for UE's and mobility between LTE and 2G/3G access networks. Mobility Management Function in LTE is now replaced with:

- **Access & Mobility Management Function (AMF)** – oversees authentication, connection, mobility management between network and device. It receives connection and session related information from the UE.
- **Session Management Function (SMF)** – handles session management, IP address allocation, and control of policy enforcement.

The Data Plane – User Plane Function (UPF) - As CUPS decouples Packet Gateway (PGW) control and user plane functions. This enables the data forwarding component (PGW-U) to be decentralized, which is mapped to the UPF for the 5G Core.

- The user plane function consists of a single entity **User Plane Function (UPF)**
- It combines functionality from previous EPC Serving-Gateway (S-GW) and PDN-Gateway (P-GW).
- UPF is responsible for packet routing and forwarding and Quality of Service (QoS).

Network Slicing - A key component of a Network Slices is the Network Slice Instance (NSI). A Network Slice instance is a set of Network Function instances and the required resources (e.g. compute, storage and networking resources) which form a deployed Network Slice (Network Slicing is implemented via Network Slice Instance(s) which are created from an NST (Network Slice Template).). In 5G, a Network Slice includes the Core Network Control Plane, and User Plane Network Functions as well as the 5G Access Network (AN). The 5G Access Network may be:

- A Next Generation (NG) Radio Access Network (gNB)
- A non-3GPP Access Network where the terminal may use any non-3GPP access to reach the 5G core network via a secured IPsec/IKE tunnel terminated on a Non-3GPP Interworking Function (N3IWF).

Network and Resource Management - Network and Resource Management consists of three parts:

- **Network Repository Function (NRF)** - Allows every network function to discover the services offered by other network functions. It serves as a repository of the services; supports discovery mechanisms that allow 5G elements to discover each other; and enable status updates of the 5G elements.
- **Network Slice Selection Function (NSSF)** - Selects the Network Slice Instance (NSI) based on information provided during UE attach. Redirects traffic to a network slice. A set of Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) are provided to the UE based on which slices the UE has access to.
- **Network Data Analytics Function (NWDA)** - Responsible for providing network analysis information upon request from network functions

Signalling

- **Security Edge Protection Proxy (SEPP)** Protects control plane traffic that is exchanged between different 5G operator networks.
- **Service Communication Proxy (SCP)** SCP is a decentralized solution composed of a control plane and a data plane. SCP is deployed alongside 5G Network Functions (NF) for providing routing control, resiliency, and observability to the core network.
- **Binding Support Function (BSF)** BSF is used for binding an application-function request to a specific Policy Control Function (PCF) instance. It is comparable to the Policy and Charging Rules Function (PCRF) binding function provided by a 4G Diameter Routing Agent (DRA) for VoLTE and VoWiFi.

Subscriber Data - Consists of UDR, UDSF:

- **Unified Data Repository (UDR)**. A converged repository of subscriber information that can be used to service a number of network functions. Stores structured data that can be exposed to an NF.
- **Unstructured Data Storage Function (UDSF)**. A repository for storing and retrieving unstructured data by a suitable network function. Network Functions (NFs) can store/retrieve “unstructured” data from UDSF.

Application Function and Network Exposure Function

- **Application Function (AF)** Supports application influence on traffic routing, accesses NEF, interacts with a policy framework for policy control.
- **Network Exposure Function (NEF)** Provides a means to securely expose the services and capabilities provided by 3GPP network functions. It exposes APIs from/to external systems.

Policy

- **Policy Control Function (PCF)** Governs the network behaviour by supporting a unified policy framework. It can access the subscription information for policy decisions taken by the UDR. Supports the new 5G QoS policy and charging control functions.
- **Charging Function (CHF)** Allows charging services to be offered to authorized network functions.

Subscriber Management

- **Authentication Server Function (AUSF)** Is in a home network and performs authentication with a UE. It relies on backend service authenticating data and keying materials when 5G-AKA or EAP-AKA is used. Performs the authentication function of 4G Home Subscriber Server (HSS) – a database that contains user-related and subscriber-related information.
- **Unified Data Management (UDM)** Is a converged repository of subscriber information; used to service a number of network functions. The 5GUDM (Unified Data Management) can use the UDR to store and retrieve subscription data. Equipment Identity Register (5G-EIR). It enables authentication of devices in the network and protects networks and revenues against the use of stolen and unauthorized devices.
- **Home Subscriber Server (HSS)** Is in 4G networks fills a similar function to the UDM for 5G. It stores customer profile data and authentication information along with encryption keys.

5G Location Services

- **Location Management Function (LMF)** Supports the following functionality: Location determination for a UE. Obtain downlink location measurements or a location estimate from the UE. Obtain uplink location measurements from the 5G RAN. Obtain non-UE associated assistance data from the 5G RAN.
- **Gateway Mobile Location Center (GMLC)** Supports the functionality to determine the location for a target device: Sends location service request to AMF for a target UE or AMF decides to initiate location, e.g., emergency call; the AMF then sends a location services request to an LMF; the LMF processes the location services request (e.g. transferring assistance data to the target device); the LMF then returns the result of the location service back to the AMF (e.g., a position estimate); the AMF returns the location service result to the GMLC.

Control Plane

- **Access & Mobility Management Function (AMF)** Oversees authentication, connection, mobility management between network and device. It receives connection and session related information from the UE.
- **Session Management Function (SMF)** Handles session management, IP address allocation, and control of policy enforcement.
- **Short Message Service Function (SMSF)** Supports the transfer of SMS over NAS.
- **UE radio Capability Management Function (UCMF)** Used for storage of dictionary entries corresponding to either PLMN-assigned or manufacturer-assigned UE Radio Capability IDs.

Access Networks

- **User Equipment (UE)** Any device used directly by an end-user to communicate (a handheld phone, laptop etc.)
- **4G/5G Radio Access Network (RAN)** Radio technology that provides access to the core network.
- **Non-3GPP Interworking Function (N3IWF)** Responsible for interworking between untrusted non-3GPP networks and the 5G Core.
- **Trusted Non-3GPP Gateway Function (TNGF)** Enables the UE to connect to the 5G Core over Trusted WiFi access technology.
- **Wireline Access Gateway Function (W-AGF)** Enables wireline access to the 5G Core
- **Non-3GPP Interworking Function (TWI)** Enables WiFi & 5G Interworking for Trusted WiFi access technology. Wi-Fi only devices (with no NAS and no SIM credentials) accessing the 5G services can be accommodated over the Trusted Wi-Fi access. In this scenario, a Trusted WLAN Interworking function (TWIF) collocated with the TNGF terminates the N1 signalling for the UE.

5G Reference points

This 5G network architecture mentions various reference points or interfaces (NG1, NG2, NG3, NG4, NG5, NG6, NG7, NG8, NG9, NG10, NG11, NG12, NG13, NG14, NG15) used between functional blocks of 5G NR network. [\[Ref\]](#)

Fig Service Based Architecture from 3GPP TS 23.501

Reference Point	Interfaces
N1	Reference point between the UE and the AMF.
N2	Reference point between the (R)AN and the AMF.
N3	Reference point between the (R)AN and the UPF.
N4	Reference point between the SMF and the UPF.
N6	Reference point between the UPF and a Data Network.
N5	Reference point between the PCF and an AF.
N7	Reference point between the SMF and the PCF.
N8	Reference point between the UDM and the AMF.
N9	Reference point between two UPFs.
N10	Reference point between the UDM and the SMF.
N11	Reference point between the AMF and the SMF.
N12	Reference point between AMF and AUSF.
N13	Reference point between the UDM and Authentication Server function the AUSF.

Reference Point	Interfaces
N14	Reference point between two AMFs.
N15	Reference point between the PCF and the AMF in the case of non-roaming scenario, PCF in the visited network and AMF in the case of roaming scenario.
N16	Reference point between two SMFs, (in roaming case between SMF in the visited network and the SMF in the home network).
N17	Reference point between AMF and 5G-EIR.
N18	Reference point between any NF and UDSF.
N22	Reference point between AMF and NSSF.
N23	Reference point between PCF and NWDAF.
N24	Reference point between NSSF and NWDAF.
N24	Reference point between the PCF in the visited network and the PCF in the home network.
N27	Reference point between NRF in the visited network and the NRF in the home network.
N31	Reference point between the NSSF in the visited network and the NSSF in the home network.
N32	Reference point between SEPP in the visited network and the SEPP in the home network.
N33	Reference point between NEF and AF.
N40	Reference point between SMF and the CHF.
N50	Reference point between AMF and the CBCF.

Service Based Interface (SBI) reference points

Figure 27 Service Based Interface (SBI) reference points

